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INNOVATION IN AN INTERACTIVE WEBSITE-BASED TEACHING MATERIALS OF INDONESIAN LANGUAGE FOR FOREIGN SPEAKERS CONTAINING THE NAMES OF FOODS DURING THE RELIGIOUS CELEBRATIONS IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

This research was motivated by the lack of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) teaching materials that thematically address the vocabulary of food names during religious celebrations in Indonesia, as well as the high demand for digital-based, contextual materials among learners and teachers. The purpose of this research was to develop BIPA teaching materials containing food names during Islamic, Christian, Catholic, Hindu, Buddhist, and Confucian religious celebrations in the form of an interactive website and to test its effectiveness in improving learners' vocabulary mastery. This research used a research and development method with the ADDIE model, which includes analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The study participants consisted of 50 BIPA learners and 20 BIPA teachers randomly selected from various universities and course institutions. Data collection was conducted through a needs questionnaire, expert validation instrument, and learning outcome test (pre-test and post-test). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, paired sample t-tests, and N-Gain. Expert validation results indicated that the product obtained an Aiken's V score of 0.846, categorized as very feasible. Implementation of the product with 50 learners resulted in an average score increase from 66.1 (pre-test) to 88.3 (post-test). The paired sample t-test results showed a t-stat of 13.62 > t-critical of 2.01 with a p-value of 2.77E-18 (<0.05), confirming that the use of the interactive website significantly improved learning outcomes. The N-Gain result of 0.634 fell into the moderate category, indicating the product's effectiveness in proportionally increasing vocabulary mastery. This research has implications for the development of BIPA teaching materials that are contextual, integrated with digital technology, and responsive to the needs of 21st-century learning.

KEYWORDS: Teaching Materials, BIPA, Celebration of Religious Holidays.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) is an Indonesian language learning program aimed at foreign nationals. This program is designed to help foreign learners learn Indonesian as a second or foreign language [1]. BIPA learning encompasses listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills [2].

In addition, this learning also includes mastery of Indonesian vocabulary and grammar. The BIPA program is offered by various educational institutions both domestically and internationally [3]. The BIPA program has become increasingly important due to the increasing communication needs of foreign nationals studying, working, and collaborating in Indonesia.

The BIPA program emerged due to the increasing number of foreign nationals coming to Indonesia for various purposes such as education, work, research, and international collaboration [4]. Their presence requires Indonesian language skills to communicate with the community, as Indonesian is the primary means of communication in everyday life. Without Indonesian language skills, foreign nationals will experience difficulties in interacting [5].

Therefore, Indonesian language learning programs are necessary to meet these communication needs. In addition to everyday communication, foreign nationals also require Indonesian language skills for academic and professional purposes [6]. Foreign students need Indonesian language to understand course material and interact on campus [7], while foreign workers need it to carry out their duties effectively [8].

Thus, Indonesian language proficiency plays a crucial role in supporting the academic and professional success of foreign nationals, as demonstrated by various research findings.

Research findings indicate that teaching materials play a crucial role in BIPA learning. Systematically structured teaching materials help learners understand the material more easily [9]. Furthermore, matching teaching materials to the learner's ability level can increase learning effectiveness. Research also shows that contextual learning materials help learners understand language usage [10]. Learners become more easily familiar with vocabulary and language structure. Based on these findings, the integration of cultural elements into BIPA learning materials is an important aspect to support more effective learning.

Research shows that the integration of cultural elements improves the communication skills of foreign learners. Through cultural integration, learners can understand language usage in real-life

contexts [11]. Furthermore, research shows that culture-based materials increase learners' learning motivation because they are directly related to the lives of Indonesian people [12].

A culture-based approach also helps foreign learners develop more authentic and contextual communication skills [13]. Furthermore, it encourages learners to participate more actively in social interactions with the Indonesian community.

Based on the results of observations conducted at several universities providing BIPA programs and BIPA course institutions, it was found that the learning materials used in learning are quite diverse and rich in themes. Available materials generally cover an introduction to Indonesian culture, traditional arts, regional musical instruments, traditional clothing, tourist attractions, and even communities' daily customs.

Several institutions have even developed digital-based teaching materials with fairly comprehensive cultural and artistic themes. However, a review of teaching material documents and brief interviews with teachers at these locations revealed no teaching materials that specifically highlight food during religious celebrations in Indonesia as the main focus of learning.

While food themes occasionally appear in the general context of Indonesian cuisine, they have not been specifically and systematically presented in the context of religious celebrations such as Eid al-Fitr, Christmas, Vesak, Nyepi, or Chinese New Year. These observations indicate a gap in the development of BIPA teaching materials, particularly regarding food vocabulary related to religious celebrations in Indonesia.

Indonesia is a country with religious and cultural diversity, including in food traditions during religious celebrations. Each celebration has its own unique dishes that serve not only as dishes but also carry symbolic meaning and cultural value. For example, during Eid al-Fitr celebration, ketupat (rice cakes; compressed rice wrapped in woven palm leaves), opor ayam (chicken in coconut milk), and cookies symbolize togetherness and gratitude [14], while at Christmas, nastar (pineapple tart) and family dishes reflect joy [15], and during Nyepi and Galungan celebrations, lawar (a mixture of vegetables, Balinese spices, coconut, shrimp paste, and minced meat) and jaja Bali (Balinese cake) are part of religious traditions [16], during Chinese New Year celebrations, kue keranjang (nian gao or Chinese New Year cake) and oranges [17], and during Vesak celebrations, there are vegetarian dishes as part of each religious tradition [18]. These

traditional foods demonstrate that food not only fulfills physical needs but also serves as a medium for conveying cultural values and beliefs.

Ketupat symbolizes purity and forgiveness during Eid al-Fitr [19], kue keranjang and oranges during Chinese New Year symbolize hope for good fortune [20], and vegetarian dishes during Vesak reflect compassion and respect for life [21]. Thus, traditional foods for religious celebrations are an important part of Indonesia's rich cultural heritage that can be introduced to foreign speakers through BIPA learning to understand the relationship between language and culture [22]. In line with this, various studies have shown that food at religious celebrations has symbolic meaning that reflects the cultural values and beliefs of the community.

Various studies have shown that traditional foods at religious celebrations contain symbolic meanings related to the cultural values and beliefs of the community. Research shows that ketupat at Eid al-Fitr symbolizes purity, apologies, and the renewal of interpersonal relationships after Ramadan [23]. At Christmas, traditional family dishes symbolize togetherness, love, and gratitude [24].

Furthermore, traditional foods such as lawar and jaja at Nyepi and Galungan celebrations reflect balance in life, harmony, and the relationship between humans and God [25]. At Chinese New Year, kue keranjang and oranges symbolize hopes for good luck, prosperity, and well-being [26]. Meanwhile, vegetarian food at Vesak celebrations reflects the values of compassion, peace, and respect for life [27].

These findings indicate that traditional foods at religious celebrations serve not only as part of tradition but also as a medium for conveying cultural values and beliefs of the community. Therefore, understanding the symbolic meaning of foods can support BIPA learning by helping non-native speakers understand the relationship between Indonesian language and culture.

Based on interviews with several BIPA instructors and learners at universities and course institutions, it was found that the theme of food names during religious holidays is considered highly potential for development in the form of an interactive website. The instructors stated that food material has a strong visual character and is more effectively understood when accompanied by images.

They also emphasized that a website-based presentation allows for the integration of authentic photos, videos, and interactive exercises that can help learners understand vocabulary contextually. From the learner perspective, most stated that they found

it easier to remember food names when presented in visual form and with quizzes or short games. Learners also expressed that the context of religious holidays makes the material more engaging, as they not only learn the language but also understand the situations in which the vocabulary is used. Furthermore, website is considered more flexible because it can be accessed at any time and allows learners to review the material independently.

A website is a collection of interconnected digital information pages that can be accessed via the internet using devices such as computers or smartphones. Website typically contains various types of content, such as text, images, audio, video, and interactive features that can be used by users [28]. Website is developed using web programming language and accessed through browser such as Chrome or Firefox [29]. The concept of a website was first introduced by Tim Berners-Lee as part of the development of internet-based information system [30]. Thus, website has become a digital medium that enables the widespread delivery of information and easy access to users in various locations.

Website has various benefits, primarily as a fast and easily accessible medium for delivering information, allowing users to obtain information anytime and anywhere without being limited by space and time.

Furthermore, website allows for the presentation of information in an engaging manner through a combination of text, images, audio, and video, making it easier for users to understand the information presented, making them an effective medium for disseminating information widely and efficiently [31].

Website is not only a medium for information, but also serves as interactive and innovative learning tools [32], as they can present learning materials, exercises, and evaluations in an integrated manner [33], increases learning motivation through attractive displays, and enables students to learn independently at their own pace. Therefore, website is an effective learning medium to support the modern learning process, and their benefits have been proven through various research findings on their use in education.

Various research findings indicate that using websites in learning can increase the effectiveness of the learning process. Website allows students to access materials flexibly without being limited by time and place [34]. Furthermore, website also helps students understand the material through more engaging and interactive presentation [35].

Research shows that students who use learning

websites have a better level of understanding than those who use conventional method [36]. This demonstrates that website can be an effective medium in supporting learning.

In line with this, other research also shows that using website can increase students' learning motivation. An attractive appearance and interactive features make students more interested in learning the material [37]. Furthermore, website also provides opportunities for students to study independently and review material as needed [38]. This helps students deepen their understanding of the learning material. Therefore, website can provide a more engaging and meaningful learning experience.

Based on the presented problems and field findings, the urgency of this research lies in the need to present innovative BIPA teaching materials that are more contextual, thematic, and digitally based. Although BIPA teaching materials have developed with various themes such as culture, art, and everyday life, there has been no development that specifically highlights food during religious celebrations in Indonesia as the main focus of learning.

Yet, these themes have high communicative value because it is directly related to social practice and authentic situation of language use. Furthermore, observations and interviews indicate a preference for interactive website-based teaching materials, which are considered more engaging, flexible, and capable of increasing learner engagement. Therefore, this research is crucial to address the gap in the development of thematic materials and to address the need for BIPA learning that adapts to technological development and the demands of 21st-century learning.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA)

Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) is a learning program designed to improve the communicative competence of foreign speakers in academic, social, and cultural domains. This program not only emphasizes mastery of language structure but also plays a role in supporting the internationalization of Indonesia and strengthening Indonesia's positive image globally [39]. In practice, BIPA learning utilizes a multimodal approach that integrates text, oral elements, visuals, and digital media to develop reading, listening, writing, and speaking skills in an integrated manner [40]. This approach provides a more contextual, varied, and meaningful learning experience for learners.

In line with the communicative approach, BIPA learning needs to integrate cultural elements because language is always related to the social context of its speakers. Language is not only composed of vocabulary and grammar, but also serves as a means of expressing feelings, ideas, and perspectives of a community [41]. The relationship between language and culture is reciprocal, as they mutually influence and shape each other [42]. Therefore, BIPA teaching materials that include cultural elements are important for

2.2. Typical Foods at Holiday Celebration in Indonesia

Cultural integration in language learning can be realized through social practices, one of which is traditional foods at celebrations of the five major religions in Indonesia. In religious and social contexts, food serves not only as consumption but also as a medium for shaping identity, values, and cultural awareness [43]. The presence of food in religious celebrations represents spiritual meaning, tradition, and togetherness that are passed down from generation to generation [44]. Thus, food has symbolic and educational value that is relevant as a source of cultural learning.

In BIPA learning, the names of religious holiday foods have the potential to become contextual vocabulary rich in cultural and religious meaning. A vocabulary teaching approach that integrates cultural elements in a balanced manner has been shown to support the improvement of learners' linguistic skills and cultural understanding [45]. The development of adaptive learning technology also enables more targeted analysis of learner responses to culture-based language tasks [46]. This demonstrates that the integration of religious holiday food names has linguistic, cultural, and pedagogical relevance in the development of BIPA teaching materials.

2.3. Interactive Websites

Utilizing digital technology is an important strategy in the development of culture-based BIPA teaching materials. An interactive website is a digital learning medium that supports two-way interaction, immediate feedback, and flexible, independent learning [47]. The development of digital learning has transformed the knowledge delivery system into a more dynamic and participatory one [48]. These characteristics make interactive website effective in supporting communicative and contextual language learning.

In the innovation of BIPA teaching materials,

interactive website enables the integration of text, images, audio, video, and quizzes in a single integrated platform. Digital technology is now widely utilized in the learning process across various disciplines, including language and content-based learning [49].

In the context of language learning, the use of technology encompasses a variety of tools and strategies that can enhance motivation and learning effectiveness [50]. Therefore, the development of interactive website-based BIPA teaching materials containing names of foods used in religious celebrations is a relevant innovation to meet the needs of language learning in the digital era.

3. MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1. Study Area

This research uses a culture-based teaching material development approach, utilizing vocabulary from traditional foods used in Indonesian religious celebrations as the primary material. The selection of the celebration context is based on Indonesia's religious diversity, which reflects the social reality of society.

This diversity encompasses six officially recognized religions: Islam, Christianity, Catholicism, Hinduism, Buddhism, and Confucianism [51]. This study selected five major celebrations: Eid al-Fitr, Christmas, Vesak, Nyepi, and Chinese New Year, as sources for developing cultural vocabulary in BIPA teaching materials.

Data on food names were collected from various cultural references, academic articles, and official sources discussing religious celebration traditions in Indonesia.

Foods such as ketupat, opor ayam, rendang (slow-cooked beef curry), nastar, kue keranjang, and lontong cap go meh (rice cake with assorted vegetables and chicken coconut curry) were selected because of their strong links to social practices and symbolic values. Many traditional Indonesian foods have philosophical meanings and serve as symbols for conveying life advice [52].

The development of this material is also based on the view that language functions not only as a means of communication but also as a medium for conveying cultural attitudes and social values [53]. The selected vocabulary was then developed into interactive website-based teaching materials containing text descriptions, visual images, video features, and interactive exercises. The use of this digital platform aligns with developments in modern language learning, which emphasize accessibility, flexibility, and personalized learning [54].

3.2. Type of Research

This research is classified as development research because it aims to create innovative Indonesian language teaching materials for non-native speakers, including the names of foods used in religious celebrations in Indonesia, based on an interactive website. This development research uses the ADDIE method.

The ADDIE method has been applied by other researchers to design Al-Qur'an therapy to address the problem [55]. The ADDIE method was chosen because it has systematic and structured stages, making it easier for researchers to design, develop, and evaluate learning products in a gradual and continuous manner.

This model consists of five main stages: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation, which are interrelated to produce products that meet user needs. Furthermore, there are revisions on ADDIE method conducted at each stage based on evaluation results, thus optimally improving the quality of the developed teaching materials. Thus, the use of the ADDIE method can produce website-based teaching materials that are effective, contextual, and appropriate to the characteristics of BIPA learners.

3.3. Participants

Participants in this analysis phase consisted of 50 BIPA learners and 20 BIPA teachers from various universities and Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) course institutions.

The involvement of these two groups of participants was intended to obtain a comprehensive picture of learning needs, both from the perspective of students as users of teaching materials and from the perspective of teachers as facilitators in the learning process. Participant selection was conducted using a simple random sampling technique.

This technique was used to provide an equal opportunity for each individual in the population to be selected as a research sample, thereby minimizing bias in the data collection process. Through this procedure, participants were randomly selected from a number of universities and BIPA course institutions that met the research criteria. Participants in the design phase included two subject matter experts and two media experts, while participants in the implementation phase included 50 BIPA learners (the same participants as in the analysis phase).

3.4. Data Collection Technique and Research Instruments

In the analysis phase, data was collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaire at this stage was divided into two parts: a needs questionnaire for

BIPA learners and a needs questionnaire for BIPA teachers. The BIPA learner needs questionnaire instrument can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Needs Questionnaire Instrument for BIPA Learners.

No.	Aspects and Questions	Options				
		1	2	3	4	5
A. Food Name Material Needs (Content)						
1	I need vocabulary material about the names of traditional Indonesian foods.					
2	I need a complete list of food names with their meanings and explanations.					
3	I need example sentences using food names in Indonesian.					
4	I need descriptive text about traditional Indonesian foods.					
5	I need practice understanding the meaning of words related to food.					
6	I need material about ingredients and how to serve food in Indonesian.					
B. Food Theme-Based Language Skills Needs						
7	I need practice reading texts about Indonesian food.					
8	I need practice writing descriptive texts about food.					
9	I need practice constructing sentences using food names.					
10	I need practice enriching my vocabulary related to food.					
11	I need examples of paragraphs about food as writing models.					
C. Interactive Website Media Needs						
12	I need interactive website-based teaching materials about food.					
13	I need pictures of food to help me understand vocabulary.					
14	I need interactive exercises (quizzes/drag and drop/fill-in-the-blank) about food.					
15	I need an easy-to-use website to learn about food.					

The needs questionnaire instrument for BIPA teachers can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Needs Questionnaire Instrument for BIPA Teachers.

No.	Aspects and Questions	Options				
		1	2	3	4	5
A. Teaching Material Needs						
1.	I need BIPA teaching materials that introduce the names of traditional Indonesian foods used in religious celebrations.					
2.	My BIPA students show a high interest in Indonesian culinary topics.					
3.	I am having difficulty finding BIPA teaching materials that focus on food vocabulary.					
B. I need materials about food during religious celebrations in Indonesia.						
4.	I need to teach the ingredients used in traditional foods during religious celebrations.					
5.	I need to teach traditional cooking/food preparation tools.					
6.	Material on how to make or cook food needs to be taught.					
7.	Material on the history of the origins of traditional religious celebration foods needs to be taught.					
8.	Material on the philosophy or meaning of food in holiday celebrations needs to be taught.					
C. Interactive Website Media Needs						
9.	I need website-based teaching materials that present food names with images and videos.					
10.	Interactive exercises such as matching food names to images will help learners master vocabulary.					

In the design stage, data collection is carried out through the preparation of flowcharts and storyboards, which serve as initial designs for the learning flow and content display on the interactive website. Flowcharts were used to map the navigation structure, material sequence, and integration of food name learning features. Storyboards were used to design the visualization of the material content, text presentation, illustrations, and the format of the exercises to be presented. Furthermore, at this stage, an instrument was developed in the form of a checklist to align the needs of BIPA learners and instructors identified in the analysis phase. This checklist aimed to ensure that each component of the

material, activity, and interactive feature fully aligned with the food vocabulary needs, communicative objectives, and the characteristics of BIPA learners' proficiency levels. Thus, the design phase not only produced a conceptual prototype but also ensured the relevance and alignment between user needs and the product being developed.

In the development phase, data were collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaire at this stage was divided into two parts: a questionnaire for material experts and a questionnaire for media experts. The questionnaire instruments for material experts and media experts can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Subject Matter Expert Questionnaire Instrument.

No.	Aspects and Questions	Options				
		1	2	3	4	5
A. Material Suitability with BIPA Learning Objectives						
1	The food names material aligns with the BIPA learning outcomes.					
2	The food vocabulary selection is relevant to the communicative needs of BIPA learners.					
3	The material is structured according to the learner's proficiency level (BIPA level).					
4	Examples of the use of food vocabulary in sentences are contextual.					
B. Material Accuracy and Depth						
5	Information about food names is presented accurately and correctly.					
6	Descriptions of food (ingredients, preparation tools, serving) are factual.					
7	There are no conceptual errors in the presentation of the material.					
8	The material is presented systematically and coherently.					
C. Integration of Material with the Context of Religious Holiday Celebrations						
9	The names of foods are chosen in accordance with the celebrations of the religious holidays being discussed.					
10	The presentation of food material does not create bias or cultural misrepresentation.					
11	The material helps learners understand the use of food vocabulary in the context of celebrations.					
D. Language						
12	The use of language is in accordance with good and correct Indonesian language rules.					
13	The sentence structure is appropriate for the BIPA learner's level of understanding.					
14	Instructions and explanations of the material are clear and easy to understand.					
15	The terminology used is consistent and unambiguous.					

The media expert questionnaire instrument can be seen in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Media Expert Questionnaire Instrument.

No.	Aspects and Questions	Options				
		1	2	3	4	5
Visual Design Aspect						
1	The website layout is neat and proportional.					
2	The color selection supports comfortable reading and is not excessive.					
3	The font type and size are easy for BIPA learners to read.					
4	Food illustrations/images are displayed with clear and relevant quality.					
B. Navigation and Ease of Access Aspects						
5	The menus and navigation buttons are easy for users to understand.					
6	The flow between pages is systematic and unambiguous.					
7	The website can be accessed well on various devices (laptop/mobile phone).					
C. Technical and Functional Aspects						
8	Interactive practice features (quizzes, drag-and-drop, etc.) function well.					
9	The website provides automatic feedback on user answers.					
10	Interactive elements support active learner engagement.					
D. Language						
11	The website runs without errors or technical glitches.					
12	Page loading times are fast and stable.					
13	All links and features function as intended.					
14	The website is secure and does not display content that disturbs users.					
15	The website supports the effectiveness of learning food names for BIPA.					

The instruments above were completed using a Likert scale. The description of this Likert scale is: 1 means strongly disagree, 2 means disagree, 3 means somewhat agree, 4 means agree, and 5 means strongly agree.

In the implementation phase, data was collected using a test method. The test instruments can be seen in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Test Instruments.

No.	Aspect	Indicator	Question Type	Question Number
1	Vocabulary	Recognizing food names	Multiple Choice	1, 4, 7
2	Meaning	Understanding ingredients and flavors	Multiple Choice	2, 3, 8
3	Classification	Classifying Food Types	Multiple Choice	5, 9
4	Sentence Use	Using Vocabulary in Context	Multiple Choice	6, 10
5	Descriptive Comprehension	Understanding Food Descriptions	Matching	11, 12, 13, 14, 15
6	Language Production	Constructing Sentences and Explanations	Description	16, 17, 18 19, 20

In this implementation stage, data was collected based on the results of the interactive website

implementation in BIPA learning. Data collection was conducted by comparing participants' learning outcomes before and after using the developed media. The instrument used was a table of pre-test and post-test comparison scores, containing each participant's score, the class average, and the difference in score improvement. This table served to identify changes in vocabulary mastery and understanding of food names after the website-based learning was implemented. In the evaluation stage, data was collected by examining the difference in pre-test and post-test scores. This difference in data allows us to determine the effectiveness of the developed media in improving BIPA learners' learning outcomes.

3.5. Data Analysis Technique

The analysis technique used in the analysis stage was descriptive statistics. The design stage utilized the Miles and Huberman concept, which has been implemented by other researchers, including data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions [56]. At the development stage, the analysis technique was carried out using a Likert scale and the results were matched with the eligibility criteria that had been used by other researchers [57] as in table 6 below.

Table 6. Feasibility Criteria.

No.	Coefficient Correlation	Validity Interpretation
1	> 0.80	High
2	0.60 ≤ V < 0.80	Quite High
3	0.40 ≤ V < 0.60	Moderate
4	0 < V ≤ 0.40	Low

4. RESULT

4. The Learners' and Teachers' Needs for Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers

Based on the results of a questionnaire completed by 50 BIPA learners, all items received dominant scores of 4 and 5, indicating a high to very high level of need. Regarding material needs (items 1–6), 86% of respondents (43 learners) stated a strong need for vocabulary materials on the names of traditional Indonesian foods, complete with meanings, example sentences, descriptive texts, and information on ingredients and preparation methods. While 14% (7 learners) stated a strong need for vocabulary materials on Indonesian food names, including meanings, example sentences, descriptive texts, and information on ingredients and preparation methods, 84% (42 learners) stated a strong need for practice reading and writing texts about food, sentence construction practice, and example paragraphs as models, while approximately 16% (8

learners) stated a strong need for practice. Meanwhile, in the aspect of website-based learning media (items 12–15), the highest percentage was seen, namely 90% of respondents (45 learners) stated that they really needed an interactive website equipped with food images and quizzes/interactive exercises, while around 10% (5 learners) stated that they needed it. The results of this questionnaire can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Result of BIPA Learners' Needs for Teaching Materials.

Based on the questionnaire completed by 20 BIPA teachers regarding the need for teaching materials (items 1–3), with a total of 60 responses, 28 responses (46.7%) scored 5, 28 responses (46.7%) scored 4, and 4 responses (6.6%) scored 3. This means that 56 responses (93.4%) were in the high category. Only 4 responses were in the medium category, thus concluding that the need for BIPA teaching materials containing food names for religious holidays is very high and almost evenly distributed among all respondents. Regarding the material needs for food during religious celebrations (items 4–8), of the 100 responses, 40 (40%) received a score of 5, 57 (57%) received a score of 4, and 3 (3%) received a score of 3. Therefore, 97 (97%) responses were in the high category. This indicates that material on food ingredients, traditional tools, preparation processes, history, and philosophy of food during religious celebrations is considered very important to teach in BIPA learning. Meanwhile, regarding the need for interactive website media (items 9–10), with a total of 40 responses, 16 (40%) received a score of 5, 22 (55%) received a score of 4, and 2 (5%) received a score of 3. This means that 38 responses (95%) were in the high category. This confirms that the majority of

respondents need website-based teaching materials equipped with images, videos, and interactive exercises to aid vocabulary mastery. Overall, the need for cultural materials (items 4-8) demonstrated the highest level of urgency (97%), followed by

interactive media (95%), and general teaching materials (93.4%). This data confirms that innovative interactive website-based BIPA teaching materials are highly relevant and much needed. The results of this questionnaire can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Result of BIPA Teacher Needs in Teaching Materials

4.2. Design of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers

The design of website-based teaching materials of

Indonesian language for foreign speakers containing the names of foods used in religious celebrations in Indonesia began with the creation of a flowchart. The flowchart can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Flowchart of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers.

After that, create a storyboard. A screenshot of one of the storyboards in the website-based Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign

Speakers, containing the names of foods used in religious celebrations in Indonesia, can be seen in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Storyboard of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers.

Menu	Content	Animation
Title	LONTONG	Text appears with a fade-in + zoom effect, rotating icon
Description	Lontong is a traditional Indonesian dish made from rice steamed in banana leaves. It is served with satay, gado-gado (vegetable salad with peanut sauce), and opor ayam.	Typed text, blurred image background to focus
Video Tutorial	"How to Make Lontong"	Play button pulsates, video slides up when opened
Meaning of Food	Symbolizes purity of heart, togetherness, longevity, and hope for abundant sustenance	Photo scrolling (slider) with fade effect, hover photo enlarges
Ingredients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rice • Banana Leaves 	The icon jumps when it appears, click the icon → description fades in

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water • Salt 	
Instruction (How to Make)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wash the rice 2. Fill the banana leaves with the rice 3. Boil for 3-4 hours 4. Cool & Cut 	Steps appear one by one with a slide to the left, with a green checkmark when complete.

4.3. Development of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers

In this section, the designed teaching materials are

then developed using WordPress. The main menu display that has been developed can be seen in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Prototype of the Main Menu of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers.

Once the prototype was completed, the teaching materials prototype was submitted to validators, both material experts and media experts, for a feasibility assessment. The results from both validators can be seen in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Assessment by Validators, Material Expert, and Media Expert.

Based on the assessments from both experts, a summary can be created as shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Correlation Table of Subject Matter Expert and Media Expert Scores.

Aspect	Subject Matter Expert	Media Expert	Difference	Description
Average V (Aiken)	0.825	0.867	0.042	Media is higher
Category	Very High	Very High	-	Equally very suitable
Highest Item	1.0 (items 2, 11, 15)	1.0 (items 8, 12, 15)	0	Equally Perfect
Lowest Item	0.625 (Item 4)	0.75 (Items 2, 5, 6, 7)	0.125	More Varied Material
Number of Items	15 items	15 items	0	Same
Interpretation	Appropriate in terms of Content	Appropriate in terms of Technique	-	Complementary

Based on the validation results by material experts and media experts, it can be concluded that the developed product has a very high level of feasibility, with a combined average Aiken V-score of 0.846. Material experts provided fairly wide variations in assessments, ranging from a low of 0.625 to a perfect score of 1.0, indicating that certain aspects require more attention. Meanwhile, media experts demonstrated more consistent assessments, with a low of 0.75 and several items reaching a perfect score. Despite differences in assessment characteristics, the two complement each other, as material experts focused more on content quality, while media experts emphasized technical aspects and presentation. Therefore, this product is deemed highly valid and suitable for use in learning, with

input from material experts for further refinement.

4.4. Implementation of Teaching Materials of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers

Before implementing the website-based Indonesian Language teaching materials for foreign speakers, which include the names of foods used in religious celebrations in Indonesia, students should be encouraged to use the product. Learners were given a pre-test. After the pre-test was completed, learners were taught several sessions using the Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers teaching materials website, which included the names of foods used in religious celebrations in Indonesia. At the end of the sessions, learners were given a post-test. A summary of the pre-test and post-test results can be seen in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Pre-test and Post-test Scores.

Component	Pre-test	Post-test
Number of Students (n)	50	50
The highest score	80	100
Lowest value	50	75
Total Value	3305	4415
Average (x)	66.1	88.3
Standard deviation (s)	9.449339	7.389858
Variance (S ₂)	89.29	54.61

Based on pre-test and post-test data, there was a significant improvement in BIPA learners' learning outcomes after the intervention. The average learner score increased from 66.1 in the pre-test to 88.3 in the post-test, a 22.2-point increase. This improvement indicates that the learning intervention using website-based learning materials was effective. In addition to the average increase, the range of learner scores also showed substantial improvement. The highest score increased from 80 to 100, while the lowest score increased dramatically from 50 to 75. This indicates that no learners were below the minimum mastery threshold after participating in the program, and some even achieved complete mastery. Another important aspect was the decrease in score variability among learners. The standard deviation decreased from 9.45 to 7.39, and the variance decreased from 89.29 to 54.61. This decrease indicates that the ability gap between learners narrowed after the treatment, the increase occurred evenly across the class, not only in learners with high initial ability but also in learners with low ability.

The pre-test and post-test scores were then tested using a paired sample t-test. The results of this test can be seen in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Paired Sample t-test Results.

t-Test: Paired Two Samples for Means		
	Post-test	Pre-test
Mean	88.3	66.1
Variance	55.7244898	91.1122449
Observations	50	50
Pearson Correlation	0.098382813	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	49	
t Stat	13.62110198	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.38678E-18	
t Critical one-tail	1.676550893	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.77356E-18	
t Critical two-tail	2.009575237	

The t Stat value of 13.62 is much larger than the two-tail t Critical value of 2.01, while the two-tail P(T<=t) value of 2.77E-18 or 0.000000000000000000277 is much smaller than the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, because the p-value < 0.05 and the t-status $>$ the critical t-value, H_0 is rejected. This indicates a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores. A learner who obtained low pre-test score provided feedback "Saya hampir tidak tahu nama makanan saat perayaan keagamaan di Indonesia. Situs ini membantu saya dari nol. Penjelasannya sederhana dan contohnya nyata [I barely know the names of foods used during religious celebrations in Indonesia. This site helps me get started. The explanations are simple and provide real examples]". Moreover, a learner with high pre-test score provided feedback "Situs ini bagus untuk pemula. Saya sudah tahu sebagian besar nama makanan, jadi saya lebih tertarik ke bagian asal-usul atau resep singkat [This site is great for beginners. I already know most names of foods, so I am interested in its original recipes]". Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of the Indonesian language teaching materials website for foreign speakers containing the names of food items used in religious celebrations in Indonesia has a significant impact on improving the learning outcomes of BIPA learners.

4.5. Evaluation of Indonesian Language Teaching Materials for Foreign Speakers

The evaluation of Indonesian language teaching materials for foreign speakers was conducted to measure normalized improvement. The results of the normalized improvement using the N-Gain formula can be seen in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Results of Normalized Improvement Using the N-Gain Formula

The analysis of 50 learners showed an average N-Gain of 0.634, which falls into the moderate category according to Hake's interpretation. This value indicates that the learning intervention implemented through the Indonesian language teaching material website for foreign speakers containing the names of food for religious holidays in Indonesia provides significant effectiveness. This figure is at the upper limit of the moderate category and approaching the high category (N-Gain > 0.70), indicating that the website has successfully helped learners close the gap between their initial understanding and ideal competency proportionally. Of the 50 learners, 18 (36%) achieved a high N-Gain (>0.70), 25 (50%) achieved a moderate (0.30-0.69), and 7 (14%) achieved a low (<0.30) category. An interesting finding is that learners with low pre-test scores (50-60) achieved an average N-Gain of 0.71 (high), indicating that they successfully closed a greater gap than learners with high pre-test scores. This aligns with the characteristic of N-Gain, which is sensitive to distance from the ideal score. Learners with low initial abilities have a greater opportunity for normalized improvement if the learning materials developed are appropriately targeted. Learners with high N-Gain stated that the material on food names used in religious celebrations was contextual and memorable because it was presented with images, videos, and example sentences. This was supported by feedback from a learner, "Saya suka bagian materi bergambar, karena saya bisa melihat langsung bentuk makanan dan mendengar pelafalannya [I like the pictorial part because I can see the food directly and hear the pronunciation]". The learners were reporting that the site navigation was clear and easy to use. However, it took time to get used to the available features. Learners with low N-Gain stated that the visuals and presentation were engaging. This was supported by feedback from a learner,

"Materinya menarik dan mudah dipahami, terutama dengan gambar dan penjelasannya [the materials are interesting and easy to understand because it contains pictures and explanations]. Results of evaluation were supported by performance matrix as viewed in table 10.

Table 10: Performance Matrix.

No	Performance Matrix	Description of Findings	Interpretation
1	Learning Completion Rate	Most students were able to complete all learning materials available on the website.	High levels of engagement and accessibility of materials.
2	Time-on-Task	Learners with lower initial abilities took longer but showed greater improvement in learning outcomes.	Website accommodated different learning speeds and supported adaptive learning.
3	Error Reduction Rate	There was a decrease in vocabulary errors between pre-test and post-test, particularly in spelling and contextual use.	Language accuracy and vocabulary comprehension were increased.
4	Engagement Indicators	The high frequency of repeated access to materials and exercises indicated active student engagement with the content.	Repetition reinforced comprehension and improved learning retention.
5	Differential Impact	Learners with lower pre-test scores had a higher N-Gain (average 0.71).	Website was effective in helping learners with low prior abilities catch up.

Thus, the N-Gain results confirm that the BIPA teaching material website containing the names of food during religious holidays in Indonesia not only increases the score absolutely, but is also proportionally effective in bringing learners closer to vocabulary mastery through the names of food during religious holidays in Indonesia.

4.6. Discussion

The results of this study reinforce the theory that teaching materials play a crucial role in supporting the success of BIPA learning. Teaching materials that are systematically designed and tailored to the learner's ability level have been shown to increase learning effectiveness and facilitate language comprehension [58]. Furthermore, contextual teaching materials enable learners to understand language use in real-life situations [59]. The relevance of teaching materials also contributes to increased learner motivation and engagement in the learning process [60]. This aligns with previous studies that confirmed that teaching materials serve as a primary support in developing the communicative competence of foreign learners [9]. In fact, the suitability of materials to the learner's ability level

and needs is a crucial factor in determining the success of the learning process [10]. In the context of this study, the increase in the average score from 66.1 to 88.3, along with the significant statistical test results, demonstrate that the development of systematic, contextual, and tailored website-based teaching materials has a significant impact on learning outcomes. The integration of various foods during religious celebrations into BIPA teaching materials also strengthens the argument that language cannot be separated from the culture of its speakers [41]. The reciprocal relationship between language and culture requires language learning to incorporate the social context and underlying values [42]. Typical foods during religious celebrations contain symbolic meanings that reflect the beliefs, traditions, and identity of Indonesian society [61]. Understanding the names and meanings of foods helps learners understand the relationship between language and culture more deeply [62]. This situation demonstrates that learning is not solely oriented toward vocabulary mastery, but also toward fostering cross-cultural awareness, as emphasized in research on cultural integration in language learning [11]. Furthermore, culturally based materials increase learner interest and motivation because they provide authentic and relevant learning experiences [63]. Thus, the integration of food names during religious celebrations not only enriches vocabulary but also strengthens BIPA learners' communicative and intercultural competencies. From a media perspective, the use of interactive websites in this study supports the finding that website-based media can increase learning effectiveness because it allows learners to access materials independently and interactively [64]. Websites, as digital media, are capable of integrating various types of content, such as text, images, audio, and video, into a single,

integrated platform [28]. This multimodal presentation makes learning more engaging and participatory, as emphasized in a study on dynamic digital learning [48]. Interactive features such as images, videos, and quizzes help learners understand the material more effectively [65]. Furthermore, website-based media allows for structured and contextual presentation of material, including the integration of cultural elements such as food during religious celebrations [66]. This aligns with the finding that the use of technology in language learning can increase motivation and learning effectiveness [50]. Thus, the use of interactive websites in this study is not only a technical innovation, but also a pedagogical strategy that strengthens the achievement of integrated linguistic and cultural competencies. The novelty of this research lies in the simultaneous integration of thematic and technological aspects in the development of BIPA teaching materials. Thematically, this research specifically highlights the names of foods celebrated during the five major religious holidays in Indonesia as the main focus of learning, a concept previously undeveloped systematically in the form of integrated digital teaching materials. Pedagogically, this research integrates the symbolic meaning of food as a means of strengthening communicative and intercultural competencies. Technologically, this innovation is realized in the form of an interactive website that has been validated by experts and tested for effectiveness through statistical analysis and N-Gain. Thus, this research provides a new contribution to the development of contextual BIPA teaching materials, based on the names of foods during the celebrations of five major religious holidays in Indonesia, and adaptive to 21st-century digital learning. This novel concept can be seen in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Novelty.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research resulted in innovative, interactive

website-based BIPA teaching materials that significantly improved foreign language learners' vocabulary mastery. The main findings demonstrate that systematic, structured teaching material design, packaged in interactive digital media, can bridge the gap between learning needs and the availability of contextual materials. This success confirms that the effectiveness of language learning is largely determined by the quality of the teaching materials and the appropriateness of the media used, not solely by the intensity of learning. Furthermore, this research demonstrates that learners with low initial abilities actually achieved the most significant improvement, indicating that teaching materials designed with appropriate pedagogical principles in mind can serve as an instrument for equitable learning quality. Thus, the development of teaching materials can no longer be viewed as an additional activity, but rather as the core of a strategy to improve the quality of language learning. It must be

carefully planned, based on real needs, and empirically tested for effectiveness.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that future development of teaching materials prioritize a needs-based approach and integration with digital technology to make learning more adaptive. Furthermore, similar research needs to be developed further by exploring other potential thematic content and testing its effectiveness across various contexts and language skills, so that future BIPA learning can be more contextual, accessible, and meaningful for foreign learners. Meanwhile, for future researchers, it is recommended to test the effectiveness of this interactive website in broader contexts, such as at different proficiency levels, across other language skills (listening, speaking, writing), or by developing other specific thematic content that also has the potential to be integrated into digital-based BIPA learning.

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